

Eco-Friendly Alternatives: A Review of the Banana Fiber Resurgence in the Textile Industry

Bharti Pahuja¹, Anu H. Gupta²

¹Department of Textile Design, National Institute of Fashion Technology, Panchkula

²University Institute of Fashion Technology & Vocational Development

Abstract:

Banana fiber, a natural and sustainable material, has been utilized for centuries, with origins tracing back to Southeast Asia, particularly the Philippines, where it was first used as early as the 13th century. This fiber, which originates from the pseudo stem of the banana plant, is highly regarded for being environmentally beneficial because it comes from a renewable source that has no effect on the environment. In the textile sector, banana fiber presents a competitive, environmentally friendly substitute for traditional cotton, whose intensive agriculture methods have serious negative impacts on the environment. India, the world's largest banana producer, generates substantial pseudo stem biomass, which can be effectively utilized to produce banana fiber. The paper reviews the potential of banana fiber as a key player in the shift towards more sustainable textile practices, given its rich history and environmental benefits. The review also explores several projects focused on banana fiber applications, identifies major industry players, and evaluates the varied spectrum of products created, emphasizing banana fiber's expanding importance in sustainable textile techniques.

Keywords: Banana fibre, Ecofriendly, Renewable source, Sustainable, Textile sector

Citation: Bharti Pahuja, Anu H. Gupta, "Eco-Friendly Alternatives: A Review of the Banana Fiber Resurgence in the Textile Industry", *Journal of the Textile Association*, **86/3**(Sept-Oct'25), 301-309, <https://www.doi.org/10.63665/xxxxxxx>

Article History : Received : 12-01-2025, Revised: 27-09-2025, Accepted: 02-10-2025

1. Introduction

- Brief history of banana fiber in the textile industry, its traditional uses, decline & resurgence

In Indian culture, the banana tree holds sacred significance due to its roots in mythology. In Hindu mythology, when Rishi Durvasa cursed his wife into becoming a banana tree for waking him, she begged for mercy. Rishi Durvasa fulfilled her request by granting the tree special status [1]. In Western mythology, Manu, also known as Hazrat Nuh in Islam, sought divine help to restore life on Earth following the great flood. He requested a plant that offered nutritional benefits and God provided the banana tree. Trees with fruit bunches are also commonly displayed at home entrances in southern India, symbolizing abundance, and fertility [2].

Figure 1: Banana fibre plant

Although it has various uses, it is mainly grown for its nutrient-dense fruit, rich in potassium, magnesium, and vitamin B6. Once the fruit is harvested, a large amount of biomass, especially from the pseudo stem, is left unused, leading to several tons of fibers being underutilized [3]. Each plant bears fruit only once, making banana fibers advantageous, as they are sourced from agricultural residue [4]. These pseudostems can be effectively utilized in production of the banana fibres [5]. India, China, and the Philippines are the top three banana producers in the world, with India leading in production, followed by China and the Philippines [6]. It is currently grown in 129 countries worldwide and ranks as the fourth most significant food crop in the world [7].

Initially, banana fiber had limited textile applications, primarily used for ropes, mats, handicrafts, and composites. In Japan, the use of banana fiber fabric, known as bashōfu, dates to the 13th century in Okinawa's Kijoka region. Bashōfu was categorized into two quality levels: premium bashōfu for fine clothing, such as kimonos for high-class individuals, and rough bashōfu for more affordable garments [8, 9]. The idea of making fabric from banana fiber may have originated from its medicinal uses, as something beneficial for health could also be advantageous when worn [10]. Historically, banana fiber has been used in textiles since ancient times, but its popularity declined with the advent of more convenient fibers like cotton and silk [11]. The early extraction process was labor-intensive and lacked standardized methods, resulting in low productivity of about 200 grams per person per day [12]. Ms. Hitomi Shinzato from the Okinawa Institute of Science and Technology noted that it takes over 23 painstaking steps to produce banana fiber clothing [13]. However, in an era of fast fashion and growing

*Corresponding Author :

Ms. Bharti Pahuja
E-mail: pahuja.bharti@nift.ac.in

environmental consciousness, banana fiber has emerged as a sustainable solution. It is biomass-derived, provides employment opportunities, and has minimal impact on soil health compared to cotton, requiring less water and no genetic modification. Furthermore, banana plants are perennial, enhancing their sustainability. Because of its environmentally favourable qualities, the market for banana fibre is expanding quickly, with a projected compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 5.50% from 2023 to 2030 [14]. This revival reflects a global trend toward natural materials and increased awareness of environmental issues.

The objective of this review is to explore

- Origin, properties, and traditional applications of banana fiber in sustainable textiles.
- Production process and recent innovations that enhance the feasibility of banana fiber.
- A comparison of banana fiber with other natural and synthetic fibers in terms of performance.
- The challenges and opportunities for the growth of banana fiber in the textile industry.

2. Methodology

This review is based on an extensive analysis of secondary data sourced from platforms, including peer-reviewed research papers, blogs, YouTube videos, market analysis, and newspaper articles. This paper aims to highlight current knowledge, identify gaps, and lay the groundwork for future research in the field of banana fibre by combining insights from these diverse sources.

3. Basics of Banana Fiber

- What is banana fiber? Origin and botanical source.

Banana plants belong to the Musaceae family [15]. The two wild species that are thought to be the ancestors of cultivated bananas are *Musa acuminata* and *Musa balbisiana*. *Musa* was derived from the Arabic name for the banana as recorded in an Arabic medical encyclopedia by Avicenna [16]. While human-consumed bananas are a member of the *Musa acuminata* species, *Musa* textiles are mostly grown for their fibre [17]. Bananas are a tropical crop that thrives in warm, humid weather with temperatures between 15°C and 35°C, fertile soil with a pH of 6 to 7.5, sufficient rainfall (650 to 750 mm during the monsoon season), and shelter from cold and strong winds [18]. Lignocellulose makes about 60% to 85% of the dry weight of banana fibre, with cellulose accounting for roughly 50% and offering structural integrity. Meanwhile, lignin adds mechanical strength and a yellowish hue [19]. The mature outer sheaths of pseudostems have a larger lignin concentration than the inner ones. Fibre composition is influenced by species and extraction techniques, and trace elements [20]. For new plants to sprout, the pseudostem which is made up of closely spaced leaf sheaths must be removed. There is a chance to turn trash into environmentally friendly products because banana plantations produce about 220 tonnes of biomass waste per

hectare [21]. Pseudostem of the banana plant produces high-quality fiber with vast potential for diverse industrial applications, including the manufacturing of textiles, sanitary pads, pulp and paper, food items, and reinforced composites used in automotive, construction, aerospace, and other sectors [22].

4. Properties of Banana fibre

Fiber morphology and chemical structure significantly influence fiber properties, leading to extensive research on fiber structures using scanning electron microscopy. Bashofu, the earliest recorded use of banana fiber in fabric production, was studied to understand its popularity. Please check analysis revealed that banana fiber fabric keeps the wearer cool in warm climates and observed various vascular bundles (fig. 2) in the plant sheath even after degumming. These vascular bundles, which transport water and nutrients, enhance the fabric's breathability by facilitating quick sweat evaporation through the pores [23].

In the same study, FTIR (Fourier transform infrared spectrometry) and XRD (X-ray Diffraction) analysis revealed that banana fiber has a crystallinity of 60-70%. Similar findings were reported in another research where internal and external fibers were compared, internal fibers showed a crystallinity index of 61.01%, with 72.81% cellulose and 9.13% lignin, while external fibers showed a crystallinity index of 66.71%, with 61.30% cellulose and 26.70% lignin [24, 25]. The natural diameter of banana fiber averaged 110.5 µm but decreased after alkali degumming due to the removal of lignin and impurities [26, 27]. The treated fiber density was 1.52 g/cm³, comparable to cotton

Figure 2: Cross section morphology of degummed banana fibre [23]

Raw Banana fiber (X100)

Raw Banana fiber(X1000)

Figure 3: Scanning electron micrographs of raw banana fibers [26]

while the length-to-breadth ratio for the wild variety ranged from 950 to 1000, lower than cotton's 6000 [28].

Banana fiber consists of helically woven cellulose microfibrils within an amorphous matrix of lignin and hemicelluloses [29, 30]. Research has shown that banana pseudostem fibre along with, jute, and sisal fibers are among the strongest natural fibers, suitable for reinforcing composites and applications like packaging, clothing, and ropes [31]. Additionally, studies have also demonstrated the thermal stability of banana fibers through DSC and TGA analysis [32].

Due to its cellulosic composition and amorphous regions, banana fiber exhibits excellent water absorbency, with a moisture content ranging from 10% to 11.5% [33]. Table 1 covers physical, chemical and mechanical properties of banana fibre.

Table 1: Physical/Chemical and Mechanical Properties of Banana Fibres [34]

Physical / Chemical Properties	Range	Mechanical Properties	Range
Diameter (μm)	80 – 250	Tensile Strength (MPa)	529 – 914
Length (mm)	1000 – 5000	Specific Tensile Strength (MPa)	392 – 677
Cellulose (%)	60 – 65	Young's Modulus (GPa)	27 – 32
Hemicellulose (%)	6 – 19	Specific Young's Modulus (GPa)	20 – 24
Lignin (%)	5 – 10	Failure Strain (%)	1 – 3
Pectin (%)	3 – 5	Density (Kg/m^3)	750 – 950

Banana fiber can be processed into yarn in different ways depending on the spinning system used. When cut and blended with cotton, it can be spun into short-staple yarn, while using a jute-spinning system allows the production of long-staple yarn. Since 100% banana fiber is difficult to card into a web, blending it with cotton in ratios such as 70:30 or 50:50 facilitates successful yarn formation in both ring and rotor spinning, with rotor spinning yielding better yarn quality. Pure banana fiber yarn can also be produced on jute machinery, achieving satisfactory strength, although it tends to exhibit higher hairiness and unevenness [35].

In summary, banana fiber's qualities, including a favorable length-to-breadth (L/B) ratio for spinning, natural shine, good absorbency, strength, and thermal stability, make it suitable for textile applications and promising for further research and a broader range of uses.

5. Traditional applications in textiles and other industries

Although banana fibre is found in abundance in tropical regions and have diverse applications still its potential has not been explored much. The major reason could be its labour-intensive extraction process and low output. There are numerous uses for banana fibre in a variety of sectors. Because of its strength and longevity, it has historically been used to make ropes and cordage for the marine, agricultural, and construction industries. Additionally, it is used in composite boards, soundproofing materials, and filtration systems. Banana fibre has been turned into pulp and used in papermaking since 1944 to make Japanese Yen notes more durable. It is perfect for making filter paper, banknotes, cigarette paper, luxury writing paper, and eco-friendly tea bags with a mesh-like material that lets water pass through while retaining tea leaves because of its strength, durability, and resistance to pests. As a biodegradable substitute, banana fibre is used in packaging to create trays, containers, and inserts [36]. The pseudo stem is used to extract banana fibre, which is then spun into yarn and woven into textiles for apparel and home goods. In South India, banana yarn mixed with cotton or synthetic fibres is used to make lightweight garments, while in the Philippines, fibres from the inner stalk are used to make delicate yet sturdy apparel, headgear, and shoes. Similar to the Philippines, efforts should be undertaken to increase the popularity of banana fibre clothing in India [37]. Banana fibre is also frequently utilised in handicrafts to create mats, baskets, caps, bags, and other

ornamental products, demonstrating its versatility and environmental friendliness. Figure 4 shows the craft of banana fiber in Anegundi avillage in koppal district of Karnataka has been thoroughly documented, highlighting traditional methods and contemporary applications [38].

Figure 4: Traditional banana fiber craft of Anegundi [38]

6. Production Process

The pseudo stems of the banana plant are cut in half, and the sheaths are removed layer by layer in order to harvest the fibres. The fibres are separated by removing the sticky cellulose like material. However, the procedure is still difficult because there are no standardised tools or methods. The earliest technique, manual extraction, involves extracting fibres using sharp tools like blades, then drying and cleaning them. Due to precise handling, the manual method yields superior-quality fibres while being labour-intensive and time-consuming, producing only about 4 kg of fibres per day. Mechanical extraction is the ideal method for large-scale production; decorticators or stripping machines can produce 20–30 kg of fibres per day. In order to separate the fibres, a revolving drum beats the sheaths. Then, residues are removed by hand combing, washing, and drying [39]. Another method is retting, which entails dissolving the lignin and hemicellulose. Despite being widespread, water retting is time-consuming, inconsistent, and bad for the environment because its effectiveness depends on factors like bacteria and water pH. Retting time can be shortened by up to 78% with controlled settings [17]. Using chemicals such as sodium carbonate, chemical retting eliminates binding components while maintaining ideal conditions to avoid fibre deterioration. For example, whiter fibres can be produced by combining hydrogen peroxide and sodium hydroxide, then neutralising any remaining alkali with a mildly acidic wash [40]. In anaerobic settings, microbial retting includes bacteria and fungi like *Clostridium* and *Pseudomonas*. This technique is less labour-intensive and appropriate for large-scale manufacturing, producing fibres that are comparable to those obtained through hand extraction [19]. Cellulase, pectinase, and lignin peroxidase

are among the enzymes used in enzymatic retting to break down lamella and smooth fibre surfaces [41]. Following extraction, the fibres are spun on a spinning wheel and subjected to common textile processing techniques like knitting, weaving, bleaching, and dyeing before the cloth is cleaned, dried, and neutralised.

6.1 Innovations and modern methods

The quality of fibres extracted largely depend on the extraction technique followed, hence, is becomes extremely important choosing the correct technique. Physical extraction techniques are mostly preferred over chemical methods since they do not severely affect the quality and quantity of fibres extracted. A recent innovation is combination of chemical and bacterial treatments which results in finer fibres. Studies have investigated the methods to improve the fineness of fibre for textile applications. The fibres mechanically extracted from the second and third layers of the pseudostem underwent both enzyme and chemical treatments. The findings indicated that the fibers treated with this combined method were the finest, with their diameter significantly reduced from 168.4 μm to 48.8 μm , representing a reduction of approximately 71% compared to fibers extracted solely through mechanical means [42].

The effects of temperature, processing time, and sodium hydroxide concentration on the physical characteristics of banana fibres were also investigated, which used a high-temperature alkali method to perform traditional fibre degumming. A residual gum ratio of 4.13% and a weight loss of 51.84% were the outcomes of processing the fibres at 140°C. The fibres' crystallinity rose to 61.33%, and it also demonstrated a breaking strength of 5.57 cN/dtex. These results demonstrate the efficacy of this sophisticated degumming technique, which is better suited for large-scale manufacturing because of its high efficiency [43]. Furthermore, banana fibres' superior antibacterial qualities point to potential uses in the apparel and bedding sectors.

7. Recent Developments and Projects

Recent advancements in the use of banana fiber have highlighted its potential as a sustainable and innovative material in various sectors. Companies, artisans, and researchers have made significant strides in developing and applying banana fiber, showcasing its versatility and eco-friendliness. These efforts not only demonstrate the fiber's potential but also underscore the growing collaboration between industry and artisans. Through partnerships and joint ventures, banana fiber is being incorporated into diverse products, from textiles to composites, reflecting a broader commitment to sustainability and resource efficiency. This section explores these recent developments and the collaborative projects driving the future of banana fiber.

Figure 5: PM Murugesan Showcases Innovative Products Crafted from Banana Fiber, Turning 'Wealth out of Waste'

- i. **Entrepreneurial Innovation in Tamil Nadu:** P M Murugesan, a school dropout from Melakkal village in Madurai, Tamil Nadu, built and patented a machine to process banana waste into rope with an investment of Rs 1.5 lakhs. His company now earns over Rs 1.5 crores annually and was praised by Prime Minister Narendra Modi in a Mann Ki Baat program ("Mann Ki Baat," 2024). Similar success stories from Madhya Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh highlight individuals crafting innovative banana fiber products that have gained domestic and international popularity [44, 45].
- ii. **Greenikk: Agri-Tech Solutions for Banana Fiber Supply Chain:** In Thiruvananthapuram, Previn Jacob and Fariq Naushad established the agri-tech company Greenikk to tackle problems in the banana fibre sector, namely irregular raw material supply and quality problems. To guarantee a consistent supply of banana fibre, they created a waste-to-value system that allowed business owners to produce high-value goods for both home and foreign markets. They tested 45 banana cultivars and chose three based on important traits including cellulose content and tensile strength. Greenikk has established training programs for micro-entrepreneurs in Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, and Kerala ("Kerala Banana Supply Chain Startup," 2023), which further increased demand for banana fibre across 12 industries, and also developed the direct-to-consumer website greenikk.shop [46].
- iii. **IKEA's Initiatives in Banana Fiber-Based Home Products:** IKEA, the global home furnishing brand, has undertaken various initiatives to promote the use of banana and other natural fibers. They have introduced several collections featuring handmade items such as plant pots, baskets, paper pot makers, plant pot covers, tool bags, carpets, cushion covers, and more. These collections, created in collaboration with artisans from

different countries, are designed to make urban gardening both practical and aesthetically pleasing, while also popularizing the use of banana fibers [47, 48].

- iv. **Saathi: Biodegradable Sanitary Pads from Banana Fiber:** Three Massachusetts Institute of Technology grads, Amrita Saigal, Grace Kane, and Kristin Kagetsu, launched Saathi, a manufacturing and social enterprise business in Ahmedabad. As an alternative to conventional non-biodegradable sanitary pads, which have been connected to health problems like infertility, cervical cancer, birth deformities, and urinary tract infections, they introduced environmentally friendly, biodegradable sanitary pads [49].
- v. **Banana Fiber-Based Bio-Composites for Wound Healing:** A recent innovation in wound healing involves the use of bio-composites derived from renewable natural resources, offering biodegradable, biocompatible properties. Researchers have developed a composite patch using banana fibers sourced from banana pseudo stems, combined with chitosan and guar gum, which would otherwise be wasted. The patch's properties were tested using various methods such as FT-IR, SEM, and tensile testing, revealing its potential for biomedical applications. Additionally, the patch demonstrated effective antibacterial activity, supported cell proliferation, and could be loaded with herbal drugs like Nirgundi for controlled release at different pH levels [50].
- vi. **Global Commercial and Textile Applications of Banana Fiber:** Companies are increasingly incorporating banana fiber into modern textile products, and actively collaborating with artisans. Eco Silky in Vietnam produces natural fabrics, while Prima Berry (UK) and Soko (Kenya) craft jewellery with banana fiber. Nudie Jeans blends it with cotton for organic denim, and Danish brand Ganni uses banana waste for sustainable athleisure. Bananatex®, a water-resistant fabric by Swiss brand QWSTION, has won international accolades for sustainability and design since its 2018 launch [51, 52].

8. Comparison with Other Fibers

Various research studies have explored the potential of banana fiber as an alternative to traditional fibers, comparing it both individually with other fibers and in blends. In a comparative study on banana (*Musa acuminata*) and bamboo (*Bambusa vulgaris*) fibers aimed at supporting bio-waste management, it was found that physically, banana fiber is stronger, denser, and has a higher water absorption capacity than bamboo. Both fibers displayed antibacterial properties, with banana fiber demonstrating greater effectiveness in this regard [53].

Further comparisons with conventional materials reveal that banana fiber exhibits mechanical properties comparable to glass fiber, making it a potential substitute for more environmentally impactful materials [54].

By altering the blend proportion and investigating a wide range of blending fibres, numerous improvements have been made to create various blend combinations. As a result of these advancements, several mixes with superior constituent fibre qualities and a wide range of applications have been created. Banana fibre may now be mixed with cotton, wool, hemp, silk, and synthetic fibres to form a range of yarns that can be used to make garments and other household products thanks to the vast research in this area. In contrast to pure cotton-Tencel blends, fabrics made by blending banana fibre with cotton and Tencel in different ratios showed a 6.61% increase in tear strength, an 18.8% improvement in air permeability, 20% more elongation, and a 12% higher tensile strength [55].

The suitability of banana fiber as an alternative to cotton has also been explored. By softening banana fibers using an innovative method and blending them with cotton in different ratios, researchers produced yarns with 14% higher tensile strength, 18% more elongation, and a 43% increase in yarn quality index compared to 100% cotton yarns. The fabrics woven from these banana-cotton blended yarns demonstrated significant advantages, including 15% higher tensile strength, 22% greater tear strength, improved airflow by 15%, and a 30% increase in friction resistance over pure cotton fabrics [56].

Banana fibre is commonly combined with cotton fibre to create yarns that are appropriate for both knitting and weaving. These yarns have a consistent tensile strength and a long-lasting texture. The 30/70 banana fiber/cotton blend made by Nisshin Textile in Japan combines the softness of cotton fibre combined with a high sheen and potent water absorption [57]. Different ratios of jute and bleached banana fibres are another popular combination that is typically used for packaging materials. A naturally dyeable blend of banana and jute fibre was successfully created by the researchers, who also looked at a number of mechanical and physical characteristics, including strength and tensile rate. According to their research, the blend is of excellent quality, has strong abrasion resistance, and does not fade colour [58]. Mixing with viscose and Tencel TM fibre are examples of further blends. The weaving properties of banana fibre are enhanced by blending it in the right ratios, changing the material from coarse and stiff to soft and skin-friendly, which makes it appropriate for sleeping fabrics and other home textiles [59].

These studies highlight the potential of banana fiber as a sustainable and versatile alternative in the textile industry, offering enhanced properties and contributing to eco-

friendly product development.

9. Challenges and Opportunities

The resurgence of banana fiber in the textile industry presents both challenges and opportunities for sustainable material innovation. As a versatile, biodegradable, and eco-friendly resource, banana fiber offers significant potential for reducing environmental impact and creating high-quality textile products. However, its widespread adoption faces hurdles, including the labor-intensive extraction process, variability in fiber quality, and the need for infrastructure to support large-scale production. There are many challenges associated with banana fibre production which includes inconsistencies in quality, economical large scale production and availability of skilled labour. To meet the market demand for banana fiber products, it is essential to address challenges such as enhancing sourcing and production methods, developing cost-effective pricing strategies, and standing out in a competitive market. Collaboration across the supply chain including farmers, manufacturers, and retailers will be crucial in responding to the rising demand for sustainable and eco-friendly products.

• Potential for growth

The ever-increasing use of banana fibres in numerous applications and its easy availability without any significant commercial value is notably driving the market growth. In addition to this, the consciousness for protection of the ecosystem is assisting the growth of many natural fibres like banana and has resulted in sustainable research environments for exploring the potential of banana fibres. The Banana Fiber Market has experienced swift and significant growth recently; with a promising outlook it is expected to grow further from 2024 to 2032. The positive market dynamics and expected further growth indicate that the market is poised for strong growth rates in the near future. By incorporation of banana fiber in different industries, very innovative products have been created which appeal to a larger audience and has generated more demand for banana fiber. These new industries include, Food packaging, Art & home décor, Fiber composites for automotive industries, Soil stabilization, Medical Textiles, Filtration, Sports equipment's, Building material and handicrafts.

The estimated compound annual growth rate (CAGR) for banana fiber market is of 5.5 % from 2023 to 2030, according to Cognitive Market Research. Overall, the market is set for substantial development. With an increase awareness for sustainability, the consumers are nowadays preferring eco-friendly products, therefore the demand for banana fiber and other sustainable materials is anticipated to grow. Additionally, continuous research and innovation in processing methods and applications are expected to broaden the potential uses of banana fiber across different industries. Banana fiber is a sustainable and versatile material with a broad array of applications. Its distinct properties, combined

with its eco-friendly nature, make it an attractive option for industries looking for alternatives to traditional materials. As the push for sustainability grows, banana fiber is set to play an increasingly important role in the pursuit of greener solutions.

10. Conclusion

Banana fiber is a promising environmentally friendly option in the textile sector, providing a sustainable solution made from agricultural waste. The revival underscores the great

potential of using natural by-products to tackle environmental issues and produce top-notch materials. The fiber is similar to traditional textiles in terms of strength, durability, and biodegradability, showcasing its versatility in various applications. Although there are benefits, it is crucial to conduct more research and invest in order to improve the extraction process efficiency and enhance the fiber's performance. By speeding up these developments, the sector can effectively utilize the advantages of banana fiber, resulting in its increased use in popular textiles. Adopting banana fiber not only lessens the load of biomass waste but also adds to a more sustainable and varied textile industry.

References

- [1] Sengupta, K. (2020, Dec 27). EVERGREEN: The symbolism of Banana plant (Hinduism) and Christmas tree (Christianity) [LinkedIn Article]. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/evergreen-symbolism-banana-plant-hinduism-christmas-tree-sengupta/>
- [2] Datta, S. (2022). Banana: A Rich Resource to Mankind. *Krishi Udyan Darpan*, 2(1), 119-121. ISSN 2583-3146. https://saahasindia.org/pdf/English_Vol2_Issue1/29.%20Banana%20A%20Rich%20Resource%20to%20the%20Mankind.pdf
- [3] Amador, L. M. V. (2018, August 20-21). Banipanel: Rice hulls and banana fiber as alternative materials in natural fiber reinforced composite panel fabrication. Paper presented at the International Conference & Expo on Recycling, Amsterdam, Netherlands. *Expert Opinion on Environmental Biology*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2325-9655-C2-021>
- [4] Ortega, Z., Morón, M., Monzón, M. D., Badalló, P., & Paz, R. (2016). Production of Banana Fiber Yarns for Technical Textile Reinforced Composites. *Materials*, 9(5), 370. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma9050370>
- [5] Balan, V. (2010). Development of preparatory processes for making of banana fiber blended fabrics and their evaluation (Doctoral dissertation, S.N.D.T. Women's University, Mumbai, India). <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/109672>
- [6] Gaddi, X. D., Alcoriza, J. M. T., Cabrera, R. T., Patricio, K. O., Santos, J. M., & Ocsan-Bulaong, D. G. (2024). Development of banana fiber yarn for crochet. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 5(5), 9309-9323. Retrieved from www.ijrpr.com
- [7] Voora, V., Bermúdez, S., Farrell, J. J., Larrea, C., & Luna, E. (2023). Global Market Report: Banana prices and sustainability. International Institute for Sustainable Development (IISD), State of Sustainability Initiatives (SSI). Retrieved from the Sustainable Commodities Marketplace Series. <https://www.iisd.org/system/files/2023-03/2023-global-market-report-banana.pdf>
- [8] Mori, R., Kakihara, F., & Nomura, Y. (2024). Premium Bashōfu and Rough Bashōfu: Producing, wearing, and discussing bashōfu, a traditional banana fiber textile from Okinawa. *The Journal of the Asian Conference of Design History and Theory*, 5, 76-82. <https://doi.org/10.18910/95348>
- [9] Hendrickx, K. (2007). The origins of banana-fibre cloth in the Ryukyus, Japan. Leuven University Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt9qf0tz>
- [10] Aoyama Square Japan Traditional Crafts. (2017, February 23). Kijoka Banana Fiber Cloth Traditional Crafts Aoyama Square [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LyzTz98VIAE&t=280s>
- [11] Kaur, A. (2015, November). Banana fibre: A revolution in textiles. *Fibre2Fashion*. <https://www.fibre2fashion.com/industry-article/7654/banana-fibre-a-revolution-in-textiles>
- [12] Mutha, Y., Mishra, R., Patil, A., Chaudhary, H., Pawar, R., & Bhagat, R. (2022). Banana Fiber Extraction Machine. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET)*, 09(01), 946-958. Retrieved from <https://www.irjet.net>
- [13] Ellenby, D. (2022, June 30). Keeping it cool: Revitalizing the traditional Okinawan craft of bashofu. *Okinawa Institute of Science and Technology*. <https://www.oist.jp/news-center/news/2022/6/30/keeping-it-cool-revitalizing-traditional-okinawan-craft-bashofu>
- [14] Deore, N. (2024). Banana fiber market report 2024 (Global Edition) (8th ed.). Cognitive Market Research. <https://www.cognitivemarketresearch.com/banana-fiber-market-report>
- [15] Maseko, K. H., Regnier, T., Meiring, B., Wokadala, O. C., & Anyasi, T. A. (2024). Musa species variation, production, and the application of its processed flour: A review. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 325, 112688. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2023.112688>
- [16] Ng, F. S. P. (2015). A brief history of bananas. *UTAR Agriculture Science Journal*, 1(1). Retrieved from [http://eprints.utar.edu.my/1673/1/UASJ_2015_Vol_1\(1\)%2C_2_A_Brief_History_of_Bananas.pdf](http://eprints.utar.edu.my/1673/1/UASJ_2015_Vol_1(1)%2C_2_A_Brief_History_of_Bananas.pdf)

- [17] Subagyo, A., & Chafidz, A. (2018). Banana pseudo-stem fiber: Preparation, characteristics, and applications. *IntechOpen*. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.82204>
- [18] Karolia, A., Doshi, A., Choudhary, K., Gupta, D., & Pathan, A. (2021). Utilization of banana pseudostem for textiles. Department of Clothing and Textiles, Faculty of Family and Community Sciences, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda. Draft report submitted to the Department of Economic Analysis and Research, National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD). <https://www.nabard.org/auth/writereaddata/tender/2803221907utilization-of-banana-pseudostem-for-textiles.pdf>
- [19] J. S., Brahmakumar, M., & Manilal, V. B. (2011). Banana Pseudostem Characterization and Its Fiber Property Evaluation on Physical and Bioextraction. *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 8(3), 149–160. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2011.601614>
- [20] Badanayak, P., Jose, S., & Bose, G. (2023). Banana pseudostem fiber: A critical review on fiber extraction, characterization, and surface modification. *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 20(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2023.2168821>
- [21] Ahmad, A., & Danish, M. (2018). Prospects of banana waste utilization in wastewater treatment: A review. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 206, 330-348. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.10.061>
- [22] Balda, S., Sharma, A., Capalash, N. et al. Banana fibre: a natural and sustainable bioresource for eco-friendly applications. *Clean Techn Environ Policy* 23, 1389–1401 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10098-021-02041-y>
- [23] Nomura, Y., Sasaki, T., Kang, H.-B., & Suwa, R. (2017). Characterization of Basho-fu material from traditional degumming process. *Journal of Fiber Science and Technology*, 73(11), 317–326. <https://doi.org/10.2115/fiberst.2017-0039>
- [24] Gomes, C. V., Araújo, J. C., Chaves, D. M., Figueiro, R., & Ferreira, D. P. (2024). Improving textile circular economy through banana fibers from the leaves central rib: Effect of different extraction methods. *Food and Bioproducts Processing*, 146, 195–204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbp.2024.06.002>
- [25] Fonseca-Pinheiro, L., de Paula Eduardo Garavello, M. E., Baruque-Ramos, J., Kohan, L., Oliveira-Duarte, L., Beserra Fernandes, P. R., Siqueira, M. U., & Figueiro, R. (2022). Banana pseudostem fibers (*Musa sp.*—cultivar AAB Prata): Physicochemical characteristics. *Materials Circular Economy*, 4(1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42824-022-00062-6>
- [26] Patel, B.H., Panchal, D.P. & Chaudhari, S.B. Per-acetic acid effect on separation of banana fiber and their dyeing with natural dyes. *Discov Mater* 4, 24 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43939-024-00086-6>
- [27] Lemita, N., Deghboudj, S., Halimi, R., & Rekbi, F. M. L. (2021). Influence of alkaline treatment time on the physical and morphological properties of a new fibre of a banana tree species. Paper presented at the First International Conference on Energy, Thermofluids, and Materials Engineering (ICETME 2021), Biskra, Algeria. *ASPS Conference Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.38208/acp.v1>
- [28] Thandavamoorthy, R., Devarajan, Y. & Thanappan, S. Analysis of the characterization of NaOH-treated natural cellulose fibre extracted from banyan aerial roots. *Sci Rep* 13, 12579 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-39229-9>
- [29] Mukhopadhyay S, Figueiro R, Arpaç Y, et al. Banana fibers: variability and fracture behaviour. *J Eng Fiber Fabr* 2008; 3(2): 39–45, <https://doi.org/10.1177/155892500800300207>
- [30] Mumthas ACSI, Wickramasinghe GLD, Gunasekera US. Effect of physical, chemical and biological extraction methods on the physical behaviour of banana pseudo-stem fibres: Based on fibres extracted from five common Sri Lankan cultivars. *Journal of Engineered Fibers and Fabrics*. 2019;14. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1558925019865697>.
- [31] Cecci, R.R.R., Passos, A.A., de Aguiar Neto, T.C. et al. Banana pseudostem fibers characterization and comparison with reported data on jute and sisal fibers. *SN Appl. Sci.* 2, 20 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-019-1790-8>
- [32] Subramanya, R., Satyanarayana, K. G., & Shetty Pilar, B. (2016). Evaluation of Structural, Tensile and Thermal Properties of Banana Fibers. *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 14(4), 485–497. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2016.1212771>
- [33] Begum, H.A., Tanni, T.R. and Shahid, M.A. (2021) Analysis of Water Absorption of Different Natural Fibers. *Journal of Textile Science and Technology*, 7, 152-160. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jtst.2021.74013>
- [34] Bhatnagar, R., Gupta, G., & Yadav, S. (2015). A Review on Composition and Properties of Banana Fibers. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 6(5). Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/367023462_A_Review_on_Composition_and_Properties_of_Banana_Fibers
- [35] Hossain, M. B., & Begum, H. (2017). Investigation of spinnability of banana fibers through yarn formation along with analysis of yarn properties. *American Journal of Engineering Research*, 6(1), 322–327. Retrieved from
- [36] Banana Fiber. (n.d.). CommonShare. Retrieved from <https://www.commonshare.com/materials/banana-fiber>
- [37] Clothing from banana fiber. (2018, April 23). *Textile Today*. Retrieved from <https://www.textiletoday.com.bd/clothing-banana-fiber>
- [38] Chandak, R., & Sathawane, V. (2015). The Banana Fibre Craft of Anegundi. *Lifestyle Accessory Design*, National Institute of Design, Gandhinagar. Retrieved from https://issuu.com/rohitr/docs/the_banana_fibre_craft_of_anegundi
- [39] Uma, S., Kalpana, S., Sathiamoorthy, S., & Kumar, V. (2005). Evaluation of commercial cultivars of banana (*Musa spp.*) for their suitability for the fibre industry. *Plant Genetic Resources Newsletter*, 142, 29-35. Retrieved from https://krishi.icar.gov.in/jspui/bitstream/123456789/2539/1/IN050668_eng.pdf

- [40] Pandey, R., Dubey, A., Krishna Prasad, G., Arputharaj, A., Raja, A. S. M., Dubey, R., Jose, S. (2024). Physico-Chemical Characterization of Lignocellulosic Seed Microfibers. *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2024.2360493>
- [41] Jacob, N., Niladevi, K. N., Anisha, G. S., & Prema, P. (2008). Hydrolysis of pectin: An enzymatic approach and its application in banana fiber processing. *Microbiological Research*, 163(5), 538–544. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micres.2006.07.016>
- [42] Balakrishnan, S., Wickramasinghe, G., & Wijayapala, U. S. (2019). Investigation on improving banana fiber fineness for textile application. *Textile Research Journal*, 89(21-22), 4398-4409. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0040517519835758>
- [43] Zhang, M., Li, M., Ye, J., Zheng, G., Wang, Z., Zhuang, X., & Muhammad, Y. (2024). Optimization of banana fibers degumming by high temperature alkaline method and spinning. *The Journal of The Textile Institute*, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405000.2024.2342761>
- [44] Raja, V. (2021, February 9). School dropout builds patented machine to turn banana waste into rope, earns crores. *The Better India*. <https://thebetterindia.com/248981/tamil-nadu-innovation-banana-fibre-mats-ropes-bags-baskets-patent-machine-national-award-successful-vid01/>
- [45] Mann Ki Baat: Madurai farmer wins PM Modi's praises for making 'wealth out of waste'. (2024, September 1). *New Indian Express*. <https://www.newindianexpress.com>
- [46] Kerala banana supply chain startup develops waste-to-value system. (2023, March 30). *The New Indian Express*. <https://www.newindianexpress.com/states/kerala/2023/Mar/30/banana-supply-chain-startup-develops-waste-to-value-system-in-kerala-2560776.html>
- [47] IKEA. (2019, December 17). Creating jobs with sisterhood and banana fibres. *IKEA*. <https://www.ikea.com/global/en/stories/people-planet/creating-jobs-with-sisterhood-and-banana-fibres-191217/>
- [48] IKEA Social Entrepreneurship. (2023, June 1). Where every piece matters – The new MÄVINN collection. *IKEA Social Entrepreneurship*. <https://www.ikeasocialentrepreneurship.org/en/news/where-every-piece-matters-the-new-mavinn-collection>
- [49] Tudu, P. N. (2019). Saathi sanitary pads: Eco-friendly pads which will make you go bananas! *International Journal of Nonprofit and Voluntary Sector Marketing*, 25(1). <https://doi.org/10.1002/nvsm.1667>
- [50] Barman, M., Rahman, S., Joshi, N., Sarma, N., Bharadwaj, P., Thakur, D., Devi, R., Chowdhury, D., Hurren, C., & Rajkhowa, R. (2024). Banana fibre-chitosan-guar gum composite as an alternative wound healing material. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 259(Part 1), Article 129653. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2024.129653>
- [51] Cernansky, R. (2022, September 8). Ganni tests banana waste tracksuit in search for sustainable fabrics. *Vogue Business*. <https://www.voguebusiness.com/sustainability/ganni-tests-banana-waste-tracksuit-in-search-for-sustainable-fabrics>
- [52] Editorial Team. (2024, January 29). Ugandan business transforms banana fiber into sustainable handicrafts. *Sustainable Suppliers News*. <https://news.commonshare.com/blog/ugandan-business-transforms-banana-fiber-into-sustainable-handicrafts>
- [53] Jeyaraj, D., Kalimuthu, M., Nagarajan, R., Chithamparam, P., Ismail, S. O., Mohammad, F., Al-Lohedan, H. A., & Krishnan, K. (2024). Biowaste management: Comparison of banana (*Musa acuminata*) and bamboo (*Bambusa vulgaris*) fibers. *BioResources*, 19(1), 1245-1259. <https://doi.org/10.15376/biores.19.1.1245-1259>
- [54] Karthick, L., Sivakumar, S., Sasikumar, A., Prabhu, A., Senthil Kumar, J., & Vadivukarasi, L. (2022). A comparison and analysis of mechanical properties of glass fiber and banana fiber composite. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 52(Part 3), 398-402. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.09.073>
- [55] Khan, A., Awais, M., Mohsin, M., Khan, A., & Cheema, K. (2024). Sustainable yarns and fabrics from tri-blends of banana, cotton, and Tencel fibres for textile applications. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 436, Article 140545. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.140545>
- [53] Khan, A., Iftikhar, K., Mohsin, M., Ubaidullah, M., Ali, M., & Mueen, A. (2022). Banana agro-waste as an alternative to cotton fibre in textile applications: Yarn to fabric an ecofriendly approach. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 189, Article 115687. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2022.115687>
- [57] Chattopadhyay, SN, Pan, NC, Roy, AN, & Samanta, KK (2018). Pretreatment of jute and banana fiber its effect on blended yarn and fabric. *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 17(1), 75–83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2018.1469450>
- [58] Hassan, M. N., Nayab-UI-Hossain, A. K. M., Hasan, N., Rahman, M. I., & Alam, S. M. M. (2022). Physico-mechanical properties of naturally dyed jute-banana hybrid fabrics. *Journal of Natural Fibers*, 19(14), 8616-8627. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15440478.2021.1966565>
- [59] Fan, Y. (2023). Study on preparation and application of banana fiber-based composites. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 2539(1), Article 012093. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2539/1/012093>

